

EFFECT OF INTERFACIAL SHEAR DEBONDING ON THE TENSILE STRENGTH AND RELIABILITY OF FIBROUS COMPOSITES: FINITE ELEMENT SIMULATION

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SUMMARY: For the purpose of clarifying the effect of interfacial shear strength on the axial tensile strength and reliability of fibrous composites, a Monte-Carlo simulation technique based on a finite element method was developed. The results showed that the interfacial shear strength value which increased the average strength of the composites corresponded to the value which decreased their coefficient of variation. The simulated strength and reliability was closely related with the degree of damage and its type around a fiber break. That is to say, small-scale debonding promotes comparatively the cumulative effect of fiber breaks and plays a role in increasing the composite strength and reliability.

KEYWORDS: fibrous composites, tensile strength, interfacial shear strength, debonding, strength and reliability, Monte-Carlo simulation, finite element method, Weibull distribution

INTRODUCTION

It is well-known that interfacial bond properties and mechanical properties of the matrix can significantly influence the tensile strength of fiber-reinforced polymer matrix composites [1][2]. That is, a low interfacial bond promotes large-scale debonding and reduces the load-carrying capacity of the adjacent fiber. On the other hand, a high interfacial bond tends to extend cracks transversely into the matrix at fiber breaks and results in increasing stress concentrations around these breaks. The same phenomenon occurs when matrices are brittle [3]. Such large-scale debonding and matrix cracking are major factors which decrease the strengths of both polymer matrix [1][2] and metal matrix composites [4]. However, there are few reports which use analytical approaches to explain these phenomena.

The present study simulates the above phenomena to clarify the effect of interfacial shear strength on the tensile strength and reliability of fiber-reinforced polymer matrix composites, using a Monte-Carlo simulation technique based on a finite element method. A boron/epoxy monolayer composite is used as the simulation model, and five hundred simulations are carried out using various interfacial shear strengths. Additionally, this study discusses the role of interfacial debonding in increasing the strength and reliability of the composites.

ANALYSIS

Finite Element and Mesh

Microdamage following fiber breaks in a fiber-reinforced polymer matrix composite is as follows [5]:

- (i) If the interface is weak, a shear stress concentration at the fiber-matrix interface often causes interfacial shear debonding along the fiber-axis.
 - (ii) However, if the interface has a strong bond, a crack initiates at the fiber break and extends into the matrix perpendicular to the fiber-axis.
- If the matrix consists of a ductile material, it yields and the yield zone spreads along the broken fiber.

Fig.1. Finite element model and mesh.

The shear-lag model [6] is widely used for estimating axial fiber stress distributions around fiber break points in a composite, simulating its axial fracture process and so on. However, the effect of (i) is not contained in the shear-lag model. Therefore, in the present study a finite element method is applied for modeling interfacial debonding and matrix cracking. The present finite element model is based on the model of a monolayer composite suggested by Mandel, et al. [7]. Figure 1 shows the model and mesh, in which a 2-node line element representing a fiber element is incorporated into the nodes along y-axis of a 4-node isoparametric element based on a plane stress condition. This plane element represents a matrix element and takes into account the multi-axial stress state of tensile and shear stresses around a fiber break. Furthermore, a shear spring element representing an interfacial bond (referred to as "interface element") connects the fiber and matrix elements. Deformation resistance of the interface element is determined by the spring constant and the relative displacement of the fiber and matrix elements. The stiffness matrix of a shear spring element is determined by the size of the bond layer and the shear modulus, similar to the formulation taken for a 2-node line element. A global stiffness matrix is constituted from the three element stiffness matrices, and therefore the whole structural analysis can be carried out following an ordinary finite element procedure. In this study a relatively brittle material such as epoxy is

used as a matrix, so that the effect of (iii) was not taken into account. Thus, it is assumed that the matrix and interface elements as well as the fiber element behave as a linear elastic body, respectively, and are statically fractured when the local stress satisfies the corresponding fracture criterion. Namely, the Young's modulus of a fiber element is changed to zero if its normal stress achieves its tensile strength. The shear modulus of an interface element is changed to zero if its shear stress achieves the so-called interfacial shear strength. For a matrix element, the Von Mises criterion is applied, in which the elastic modulus of the element is changed to zero if its equivalent stress achieves its tensile strength. In the remainder of this article, we call their fractures "damages", and individually we call them fiber break, interfacial debonding and matrix fracture, respectively.

The composite model used in this study is a boron/epoxy monolayer composite, and the finite element mesh has ten fibers of which each is divided into twenty elements. The number of nodes is 462, and the numbers of fiber, matrix and interface elements are 200, 220 and 190, respectively.

(a) Method 1

(b) Method 2

Fig.2. Calculation methods for fiber-break process.

Simulation Procedure

Occurrences of fiber breaks, matrix fracture and interfacial debonding would cause complicated stress distributions throughout a composite. Therefore, a method for estimating reasonably what type of damage occurs in each element, should be incorporated within the simulation procedure. In order to achieve such an estimation, an r -minimum method [8] is employed in this study, which was originally used in searching for yielding regions in a metal with an elastic-plastic finite element method. According to this method, a ratio of the

difference between strength and stress in each element to the stress increment is calculated, and the element giving the minimum ratio takes precedence for the damage, i.e. the fiber break, the matrix fracture or the interfacial debonding. The following is the present simulation procedure:

1. A strength of a fiber element obeys the following 2-parameter Weibull distribution:

$$F(\sigma) = 1 - \exp \left\{ - \frac{L}{L_0} \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^m \right\} \quad (1)$$

where, m and σ_0 are the Weibull shape and scale parameters, L is an arbitrary fiber length, and in this study is equivalent to the fiber element length, L_0 is a standard gage length at which the Weibull parameters are estimated. By substituting a uniform random number into the inverse function of eqn 1, we can generate a random Weibull strength to assign to a fiber element.

2. The unknown nodal displacements Δu_i are computed under the boundary condition of displacement increment at the fiber and matrix ends, as shown in Fig.1. The computation is carried out incrementally, but the increment width is not fixed. In this study an arbitrary large increment ΔU enough to damage almost all the elements was given to the ends even at the first calculation stage. The stresses and the stress components acting in the elements are calculated from the computed displacements. Then, the ratios r are calculated for all the elements.

3. Next, a possibility of the damage occurrence and its type are determined by the r_{min} method. The outcome will change the boundary condition, as shown in Fig.2 and as follows,
 i) If $r_{min} \leq 1$, all the stresses calculated in this stage are modified to the exact stresses by multiplying r_{min} with the stress increment in each element (see Fig.2 (a)). Then the [D] matrix components of the element giving the r_{min} are changed to zero. If this element is a fiber element or a matrix element, then in the next stage the load P_i acting in this element is released through its nodes along y -axis under the boundary condition of load increment and the fixed condition at the fiber and matrix ends (see Fig.2 (b)). If $r_{min} \leq 1$ is still satisfied, the next stage is consumed to release the load acting in the new damaged element, together with the residual load of the previous stage in the same way. This procedure is repeated until $r > 1$.
 ii) If $r_{min} > 1$, then damage does not occur. The boundary condition of displacement increment is applied again at the fiber and matrix ends, as described in 2.

4. As the damage accumulates in a composite, the support force along y -axis begins to decrease largely at a certain strain level. It was assumed that when such behavior occurs, or when the composite stress achieves a stress level less than 80% of the maximum stress, the composite fracture criterion is satisfied.

Table 1. Material constants used in the present simulation

Young's modulus of boron fiber	397.9 GPa
Diameter of boron fiber	0.142 mm
Fiber element length	0.3 mm
Weibull shape parameter for fiber strength	7.16
Weibull scale parameter for fiber strength at 6mm	3.665 GPa
Young's modulus of epoxy matrix	3.296 GPa
Poisson's ratio of epoxy matrix	0.39
Tensile strength of epoxy matrix	45.57 MPa
Thickness of matrix element	0.371 mm
Shear modulus of interface element	1.186 GPa
Thickness of interface element	0.142 mm
Width of interface element	1.42 mm
Distance between fibers	0.259 mm

5. Following the above procedure, five hundred of simulations were carried out under different sets of random numbers. Finally the average and coefficient of variation in the simulated strengths were calculated.

The present study simulates the tensile strength and reliability of a boron/epoxy monolayer composite. In Table 1, the material constants used in the present simulation are shown. The Weibull parameters of the boron fiber (Boron/Tungsten 5.6mil, AVCO) and the tensile strength of the epoxy resin (Arardite CY230/Hardener HY2967, Ciba-Geigy Co.) were determined experimentally.

RESULTS

Effect of interfacial shear strength on the strength and reliability

Figure 3 shows typical stress-strain curves of the simulation results. In the computation, interfacial shear strengths, $\tau_1 = 11.7, 20.4$ and 35.0 MPa were used under the same set of random numbers for fiber strength. Therefore the stress levels at the first fiber break are all the same, but the behavior following the break is completely different. Figure (a) shows a similar fracture process to that of a bundle consisting of small number of fibers. That is, the first fiber break indicates the maximum stress and is followed by the other individual fiber breaks which occur at stress levels less than maximum. However in figure (b) the level of the second peak is larger than the first level and indicates the maximum stress. Figure (c) shows that the stress level drops in a moment after the first peak, though recovering slightly around 0.8% strain. These results show that $\tau_1 = 20.4$ MPa gives the highest strength, and imply that the more cumulative fiber break pattern increase the composite strength.

Fig.3. Simulated stress-strain diagrams of a boron/epoxy composite.

Fig.4(a) Effect of interfacial shear strength on the average tensile strength. (IFSS: Interfacial shear strength)

Fig.4(b) Effect of interfacial shear strength on the coefficient of variation in strength.

Figure 4 (a) and (b) shows the effect of the interfacial shear strength on the average and coefficient of variation in simulated strengths, respectively. Solid symbols at $\tau_i = 0 \text{ MPa}$ in the

figure indicates the results of 5000 bundle simulations. The results show that the average strength shown in open circles gradually increases with increasing interfacial shear strength, but decreases after the peak at $\tau_i=20.4\text{MPa}$. The coefficient of variation shown in open triangles decreases up to $\tau_i=23.3\text{MPa}$ and then increases abruptly. It is predicted from both of the behaviors that there is an optimum interfacial shear strength which improves the strength and reliability of the composite around $\tau_i=20\text{MPa}$. The shear strength of epoxy is estimated to be 26.3MPa according to Von Mises' criterion. Figure 4 also implies that an optimal interfacial shear strength introduced in the above could be slightly less than 26.3MPa . Note that the averages and coefficients of variation result in almost the same values for levels of $\tau_i=29.1\text{MPa}$ and more. This is because matrix fracture, assumed to be a deterministic phenomenon, governs most of the damages following fiber-breaks.

In Fig.4(a) and (b) the effect of random interfacial shear strength is additionally indicated (solid squares). It is implied that the interfacial shear strength is a random variable with a relatively large variation [9]. So, random interfacial shear strengths were assigned to all the interface elements, on the condition that the interfacial shear strength obeys a 2-parameter Weibull distribution. The Weibull shape parameter was assumed to be 2.5, in order to express a large variation. As the representative interfacial shear strength value in plotting the results, 'median' was selected. Since a median is a function of the Weibull scale parameter, composite strengths with random interfacial shear strengths were simulated by changing this parameter. In Fig.4(a) the average strength shown in solid circles gradually increases with increasing the interfacial shear strength (i.e. the median, τ_M) in the similar way to that in the constant interfacial shear strength, and the peak is indicated at $\tau_M=17.5\text{MPa}$. In Fig.4(b) the minimum of the coefficients of variation is also seen in at $\tau_M=17.5\text{MPa}$. The both statistics are inferior to the peak and minimum given in the constant interfacial shear strength. However, this inferiority is reversed at $\tau_M=29.1\text{MPa}$ and 35.0MPa .

Stress distributions around a broken fiber element

It is considered that stress-strain behaviors and strengths of the composite are closely related with the degrees of matrix and interfacial damages following fiber breaks. Figure 5 shows the fiber stress distributions around a broken fiber element simulated for $\tau_i=11.7, 20.4$ and 35.0MPa , on the condition of the constant interfacial shear strength. In the figure the fiber element, fifth from the left-hand and tenth from the fiber end, was broken intentionally at the fiber stress of 1960MPa . Figure 6 shows the damage states of the matrix and interface obtained in the above simulations. The stress distributions on the fiber elements adjacent to the broken element are shown in Fig.5 (a), in which the largest stress acts on the nearest fiber element. The degree of the stress concentration depends largely on the interfacial shear strengths. That is to say, the strongest bond, i.e. $\tau_i=35.0\text{MPa}$, propagates matrix fractures into the surrounding matrix elements, as shown in Fig.6(c), and gives the largest stress concentration. On the other hand, the lowest interfacial shear strength, i.e. $\tau_i=11.7\text{MPa}$, promotes large-scale debonding, as shown in Fig.6(a), and gives the lowest stress concentration, as shown in Fig.5(a). Figure 5(b) shows the stress distributions of fiber element along the broken fiber. Since in $\tau_i=35.0\text{MPa}$ the load-carrying capacity of the broken fiber is reduced, particularly in the region where the matrix fractures occur, the stress recovery is delayed. The weakest bond, i.e. $\tau_i=11.7\text{MPa}$, yields the poorest load-carrying capacity for the broken fiber, due to large-scale debonding. The intermediate value for bond strength, i.e. $\tau_i=20.4\text{MPa}$, yields small-scale debonding and brings the highest load-carrying capacity. Figures 5 and 6 imply that there is an appropriate interfacial shear strength which can generate

a state with a relatively small stress concentration around broken fibers and a high load-carrying capacity for broken fibers. And the appropriate bond strength can possibly increase the composite strength, as shown in the previous section. Such a relation between composite strength and matrix damage is verified in the experiment in which the effect of interfacial bond on the tensile strength of a boron/ epoxy composite is investigated [2].

(a) Stress concentration on fiber elements perpendicular to fiber-axis

(b) Stress recovery of broken fiber element along fiber-axis

Fig.5. Fiber stress distributions around a broken fiber element.

Fig.6. Damages of matrix and interface around a broken fiber element.

In Fig.4(a) and (b) random interfacial shear strengths decrease the optimum values for the average and coefficient of variation. It is predicted from the above stress distributions that the effect of large-scale debonding still remains due to its random nature, even if the median of interfacial shear strength increases. Therefore, the both statistics are not improved. Conversely, the effect of small-scale debonding still appears in the random interfacial shear strength with large medians, and therefore its averages and coefficients of variation are superior to those in the constant interfacial shear strength at $\tau_M = 29.1$ MPa and 35.0 MPa, respectively.

DISCUSSION

It was shown that the small and large interfacial shear strengths cause large-scale debonding and matrix fracture, respectively, and they both reduced the average composite strength. On the other hand, the intermediate values of interfacial shear strengths resulted in increased average strength. However why do the interfacial shear strengths increasing the average yet also produce the low coefficients of variation? The author considers that the strength and reliability of fibrous composites is closely related with damage accumulation up to the maximum stress, which in this study is equivalent to the number of broken fiber elements. For example, in Fig.3(a), (b) and (c) these numbers are 1, 2 and 1, respectively (referred to as "i-break"). Figure 7 shows the ratio of the number of broken fiber elements to the total number of simulations versus the constant interfacial shear strength. In the present simulation most of composites indicated 1-, 2- or 3-break, and four or more breaks was not a major figure (in any case approximately 1 to 3 %). The transition of the ratio is comparable to that shown in Fig.4. That is to say, the ratio of 1-break, non-cumulative failure mode, shows the minimum value at $\tau_i = 17.5$ MPa, and increases up to around 0.5 with an increase in interfacial shear strength. On the other hand, the ratio of 3-break or more, cumulative failure mode, behaves to be contrary to the case of 1-break. Namely, this ratio gives the peak at $\tau_i = 17.5$ MPa, and then decreases to

a value less than 0.2 and shows almost a constant. In the case of 2-break, intermediate failure mode, the ratio shows approximately a constant, though it keeps a slightly higher level at $\tau_i=11.7$ MPa to 23.3 MPa. Such a correspondence to Fig.7 tells us that a composite with large-scale debonding and matrix fracture yield a smaller number of fiber breaks than a composite with small-scale debonding. If failure of the weakest fiber in a composite immediately leads to composite fracture without accumulation of fiber breaks, the variability in composite strength will reflect that in fiber strength and represent an upper bound^{*1}. In other words a less cumulative failure mode will approach to this degree of scatter. Therefore both small and large interfacial shear strengths induce significant scatter in composite strength. On the other hand, more cumulative fiber breaks further increases the stress level, so that the strength distribution of survival fibers would shrink in width toward the upper side. The shrinkage might be concerned with decreasing a scatter in composite strength. Such a situation accompanied with the more cumulative fiber breaks is generated by small-scale debondings, and therefore contribute to improving the strength and reliability of composites.

Fig.7. Ratio of the number of broken fiber elements to the total number of simulations vs. interfacial shear strength.

CONCLUSION

A Monte-Carlo simulation technique based on a finite element method was developed in order to uncover the effect of interfacial shear strength on the tensile strength and reliability of fibrous composites. In the simulation a boron/epoxy monolayer composite with ten fibers was

modeled, and five hundreds simulations were carried out using various interfacial shear strengths. The main results of this work were as follows:

(1) The interfacial shear strength value which increased the average strength of the composites corresponded to the value which decreased their coefficient of variation. This implied an existence of an optimum value of interfacial shear strength which can increase the strength and reliability. This value was estimated to be slightly less than the matrix shear strength.

(2) The simulated strength and reliability was closely related with the degree of matrix damage and its type following a fiber break. Large-scale debonding and matrix fracture reduced the number of fiber breaks accumulated up to the maximum achieved stress, and decreased the strength and reliability. On the other hand, small-scale debonding promoted comparatively the cumulative effect of fiber breaks and play a key role in increasing composite strength and reliability.

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*1 If a composite consists of N fibers and the fiber strength follows a 2-parameter Weibull distribution, the distribution function for the weakest fiber strength is given as the minimum distribution of N Weibull distributions, i.e. the first order statistic. This form is also a 2-parameter Weibull distribution, and the shape parameter agrees with that in its population.